

Impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on Undergraduates' Lecture Attendance and Punctuality in Ogun State Universities

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Abstract

The study examined the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance and punctuality in Ogun State. Six research questions guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population comprised 3,054 undergraduates of Tai Solarin Federal University of Education (TASUED) and Olabisi Onabanjo University (OOU). A total of 230 undergraduates of selected universities were chosen as sample size of the study using stratified sampling technique. Researchers' designed instrument tagged Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and Undergraduates' Lecture Attendance and Punctuality Questionnaire (HCIUDLAPQ) with ($r = .86$) as reliability coefficient was used for data collection. Frequency counts and percentages were used for presenting demographic characteristics of the respondents. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used for answering research questions 1, 2, 3 and 4. Research questions 5 and 6 were answered using PPMC. The findings of the study revealed that there were high level of undergraduates' lecture attendance ($2.97 > 2.50$) and punctuality ($3.14 > 2.50$). Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) impact on undergraduates' lecture attendance ($2.95 > 2.50$) and punctuality ($2.78 > 2.50$) in Ogun State universities. There was positive relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), undergraduates' lecture attendance ($r = 0.007, p < .05$) and punctuality ($r = 0.022, p < .05$) in Ogun State Universities. The study concluded that Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) has a positive relationship as well as impact on undergraduates' lecture attendance and punctuality. It was recommended that tertiary institutions management should develop a policy for awarding marks to students who attend lectures, this will encourage those students who have a negative attitude to lectures. Also, as a way forward, mandatory attendance should be enforced and lecturer should adopt a friendly posture and encourage students to be punctual in the class.

Keywords: Human-Computer Interaction, Undergraduates, Lecture Attendance, Punctuality

Introduction

In a lecture-room setting, student attendance is the practice of tracking which students are physically present in class. This process is considered vital for academic success, student engagement, and accountability. Students benefit from the lecturer's expertise, clarification of complex concepts, and emphasis on key topics that may appear on exams. Being present allows students to ask questions, participate in discussions and group activities, and receive timely feedback, which deepens understanding. Attending class helps students establish connections with teacher and peers, fostering a support system and a sense of belonging within the institution. Even, consistent attendance instills self-discipline and a strong work ethic, preparing students for future

professional environments and attendance data can serve as an early warning indicator for academic or personal problems, allowing institutions to offer timely support (Antunes et al., 2024). However, numbers of observations have indicated that students' attendance and punctuality in lecture-room as same thing, but they are not. Student punctuality in a lecture room encompassed students arriving on time, being prepared for the lesson, and respecting the time of both the lecturer and peers. This habit of arriving on time demonstrates respect for the lecturer's and classmates' time and the learning environment as a whole.

Student punctuality offers benefits like improved time management, better academic performance by not missing lessons, reduced stress from avoiding last-minute rushes, and building essential life skills such as discipline, responsibility, and a strong work ethic that foster self-confidence and a positive reputation. It sets a tone for focus and readiness, making students more engaged learners and better prepared for future careers (Austin, 2022). In another word, student punctuality means arriving on time ensures students do not miss crucial instructions, discussions, or the beginning of lessons, leading to better comprehension and retention (Vera et al., 2022). Punctual students are more likely to be engaged, complete work thoroughly, and meet deadlines, boosting overall grades and starting class on time minimizes classroom disruption and helps students settle in, fostering a more focused learning environment.

The emergence of computer and it is instrumental tools in the field of education, most especially in instruction delivery process have received a positive welcome from the literature (Ebibi et al., 2023; Lawrence & Ashleigh, 2023). Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) is a multidisciplinary field studying how student interact with computers and designing user-friendly interfaces to make technology intuitive, efficient, and accessible, blending computer science, design, psychology, and cognitive science to create seamless user experiences. It focuses on the interface, the visual, auditory, or tactile means of communication and aims to optimize the user experience (UX) through research, design, and testing, ensuring technology meets human needs (Ebibi et al., 2023). The design process focuses on the student's needs, goals, prior knowledge, cognitive abilities (like memory and attention), and physical characteristics.

HCI considers the conditions under which the student interacts with the technology, such as using a phone in a noisy environment or a laptop in a quiet dorm room, to ensure optimal performance. (Mubarak et al., 2023). According to Ragu-Nathan et al. (2018), well-designed educational software and interactive programs can make learning more engaging and effective by providing instant feedback and adapting to different learning styles. By applying HCI principles, technology becomes more user-friendly, reducing frustration and errors, and allowing students to focus on their studies rather than figuring out the technology itself. Osisanwo and Ehioghae (2022) claimed that HCI research is crucial for developing assistive technologies (e.g., screen readers, voice recognition) that ensure students with disabilities have equal access to educational resources and tools. HCI provides students with essential skills for professions such as user experience (UX) design, interaction design, and software engineering, all of which are in high demand in the tech industry and it is about designing technology with people in mind, making digital interactions as intuitive and natural as human-to-human communication (Mubarak et al., 2023). Lawrence and Ashleigh (2023) observed that by applying HCI design principles, educational technology can be made more interactive and engaging, using elements like gamification, clear visual feedback, and personalized interfaces to capture and maintain student interest. And that well-designed interfaces can foster a sense of accomplishment and control, directly contributing to student motivation and willingness to interact with the learning material.

HCI research helps design information architecture that reduces cognitive load, allowing students to process and retain information more effectively as well as designing clear, timely, and constructive feedback loops within educational software, guided by HCI principles, helps students understand their progress and areas for improvement (Lalitha & Sami, 2022). HCI aids in the development of user-friendly interfaces for virtual classrooms, discussion boards, and group projects, making online collaboration as smooth and natural as possible and well-designed communication tools facilitate effective and efficient interaction between students and instructors, ensuring that support is easily accessible (Jena, 2022). Thus, according Damiete and Melanie (2019), the importance of HCI lies in its ability to bridge the gap between technology and the user (the student), transforming digital tools from complex machines into intuitive, powerful aids that directly support and enhance the educational journey.

Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) could aid student attendance in a lecture room by designing intuitive and efficient systems that encourage participation and minimize friction in the tracking process (Monideepa et al., 2022). The core principle of HCI in this context is to create a seamless, user-centered experience that benefits both students and lecturers. Instead of requiring students to manually sign a sheet or type long codes, HCI principles push for ambient, automatic check-ins. By focusing on user-centered design, efficiency, and engagement, HCI transforms attendance tracking from an administrative burden into a seamless, reliable, and potentially motivating part of the educational experience (Casey, 2023). In the opinions of Lee et al. (2023), Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) can aid student punctuality in a lecture room by leveraging technology to provide timely information, increase personal accountability, and streamline logistical processes. In that way, HCI systems can deliver highly personalized and context-aware alerts directly to students' devices (smartphones, smartwatches. An application could use GPS to detect when a student is a certain distance from the lecture hall and hasn't yet started their commute, sending an alert that says, "Lecture starts in 20 minutes; you are 15 minutes away. Notifications can intelligently adapt based on a student's schedule, traffic conditions, or public transport delays, providing actionable information rather than just a generic time reminder. Smartwatches can provide subtle, non-intrusive haptic feedback (vibrations) to remind students to leave for class without disrupting their current activities. Designing clearer, more accessible interfaces for displaying class schedules and locations reduces the cognitive load associated with finding information, making it easier for students to be in the right place at the right time. Interactive digital signage near common student areas or an intuitive mobile app interface can show immediate changes in room numbers or lecture cancellations, preventing wasted trips (Booker & Rebman, 2021).

Furthermore, campus navigation apps designed with strong HCI principles can offer turn-by-turn directions optimized for efficient travel between buildings, especially helpful for new students or complex campuses. HCI principles can be used to design systems that encourage positive behavioral changes through engagement and social pressure (Baral & Sharma, 2019). In the word of Carneiro et al. (2016), user interfaces that clearly track and display a student's personal attendance record over time can make lateness metrics visible, fostering a sense of personal responsibility. Implementing a system where students earn points, badges, or "punctuality streaks" for on-time arrivals can make attendance a more engaging activity, using a reward system common in effective user interfaces. Booker and Rebman (2021) concurred that utilizing facial recognition or proximity detection to log attendance automatically removes the need for manual check-ins, allowing students to flow seamlessly into the lecture room.

Statement of the Problem

Although, student attendance and punctuality in lectures offer numerous benefits that significantly contribute to academic success and professional development. However, students often struggle with managing their time effectively, leading to late nights spent watching films, socializing, or working on other assignments, which results in waking up late and rushing in the morning. A lack of personal interest in the subject, a perception that attending lectures is not essential for passing exams, or a belief that material can be learned better through other means (like online notes or YouTube) can significantly lower a student's motivation to attend on time. Even, students lacking technical proficiency may struggle to navigate learning management systems (LMS) or university portals where lecture schedules, room changes, and important updates are posted. This confusion can lead to missed classes or delayed arrival times. However, this study was an attempt to examine how undergraduates lecture attendance and punctuality could be increased through Human-Computer Interaction (HCI).

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance and punctuality in Ogun State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. identify the level of undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities;
2. ascertain the level of undergraduates' lecture punctuality in Ogun State Universities;
3. find out the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State universities;
4. determine the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture punctuality in Ogun State universities;
5. examine the relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities;
6. ascertain the relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates' punctuality in Ogun State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the level of undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities?
2. To what level are undergraduates' punctual in lecture in Ogun State Universities?
3. What are the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State universities?
4. What are the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture punctuality in Ogun State universities?
5. Is there any relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities?
6. Is there any relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates' punctuality in Ogun State Universities?

Research Methods

A descriptive research survey design was adopted for the study. The justification for using a descriptive research survey design centers on understanding the "what, where, when, and how" of a phenomenon by describing a population's characteristics, behaviors, or trends, not the "why" (causality). It's ideal for initial research, establishing a baseline, identifying patterns, validating existing conditions, and informing future studies, offering a cost-effective, efficient snapshot of a large group's attitudes,

preferences, or demographics. The population of this study comprised 3,054 undergraduates of Tai Solarin Federal University of Education (TASFUED) and Olabisi Onabanjo University (OOU). A total of 230 undergraduates of selected universities were chosen as sample size of the study using stratified sampling technique. Researchers’ designed instrument tagged Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and Undergraduates’ Lecture Attendance and Punctuality Questionnaire (HCIUDLAPQ) was used for this study. HCIUDLAPQ was used for the collection of data from respondents regarding level of undergraduates’ lecture attendance; level of undergraduates’ lecture punctuality; contributions of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates’ lecture attendance and contributions of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates’ lecture punctuality. The questionnaire requested responses on a four (4) – point scale format which was a modification of 5-point Likert scale. To ensure the face validity of the instrument (HCIUDLAPQ), copies of the instrument were given to experts in the Department of Educational Technology, Tai Solarin Federal University of Education (TASFUED). Reliability test of the instrument (HCIUDLAPQ) was done using a test-retest method. In this case, copies of the instrument (HCIUDLAPQ) were administered twice on 10 final year undergraduates in Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta (FUNAAB), that are not part of the study within a week interval. The collected data from the dual administration of the instruments were compared using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and a reliability coefficient 0.86 was reported. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used for answering research questions 1, 2, 3 and 4. Research questions 5 and 6 were answered using PPMC.

Results

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of undergraduates’ lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation responses on the level of undergraduates’ lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
I resume lectures in the first week of resumption.	2.81	.944
I regularly attend to lectures.	3.04	.695
My colleagues’ absenteeism rate is high in lectures.	3.07	.611
My colleagues’ mostly attend lectures on Monday.	3.11	.609
I mostly attend lectures on Tuesday.	3.21	.613
I often attend lectures on Wednesday.	2.78	.784
I often attend lectures on Thursday.	2.92	.721
I often attend lectures on Friday.	2.84	.699
I attend lectures to listen to what lecturer want to teach.	3.16	.667
I attend lecture to improve my academic performance.	2.78	.902
Cluster Mean	2.97	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 showed that cluster mean was 2.97 which found to be greater than bench mark value 2.50. This implied that there was high level of undergraduates’ lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities.

Research Question 2: To what level are undergraduates’ punctual in lecture in Ogun State Universities?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation responses on the undergraduates' punctual in lecture in Ogun State Universities

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
I am punctual to lectures.	3.16	.661
I arrive lecture before other students.	3.14	.651
I come to lecture room early to seat in the front.	3.08	.689
Coming to lecture room before lecture start is now my habit.	3.07	.633
Attending lectures always have helped my behavior towards better performance.	3.11	.672
Attending lecture helps my subject clarity and understanding.	3.29	.600
Cluster Mean	3.14	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 indicated that cluster mean was 3.14 which greater than the bench mark mean value. The implications of this result were that there was high level of punctuality in lecture in Ogun State Universities.

Research Question 3: What are the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State universities?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation responses on the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State universities

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
HCI allows students to have access to online materials.	2.74	.981
It promotes students' behavior towards lecture attendance.	2.59	.996
It shows case the benefits of lecture attendance to students.	2.99	.909
It motivates undergraduates towards interactive computing among peer.	3.26	.911
It always encourages me to seeks further information on new issues.	3.21	.700
HCI allows students to have access to online materials.	2.88	.945
Cluster Mean	2.95	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 revealed that cluster mean was 2.95 which greater than the bench mark mean value of 2.50. The implications of this result were that allows students to have access to online materials, promotes students' behavior towards lecture attendance, shows case the benefits of lecture attendance to students, motivates undergraduates towards interactive computing among peer, always encourages to seeks further information on new issues and allows students to have access to online materials were among the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State universities.

Research Question 4: What are the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture punctuality in Ogun State universities?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation responses on the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates’ lecture punctuality in Ogun State universities

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
HCI guide undergraduates’ interaction for lecture punctuality.	2.84	.909
It teaches students on the need for computer for punctuality.	2.74	.967
It helps students for self-evaluation that encourages lecture punctuality. .	2.56	.982
It improves the quality of interaction among students and computer that lead to lecture punctuality.	2.83	.907
It gives undergraduates’ excellent experience between computer and its benefits for lecture punctuality.	2.94	.914
Cluster Mean	2.78	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4 depicted that cluster mean was 2.78 which greater than the bench mark mean value of 2.50. The implications of this result were guide undergraduates’ interaction for lecture punctuality, teaches students on the need for computer for punctuality, helps students for self-evaluation that encourages lecture punctuality, improves the quality of interaction among students and computer that lead to lecture punctuality, and gives undergraduates’ excellent experience between computer and its benefits for lecture punctuality were among the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates’ lecture punctuality in Ogun State universities.

Research Question 5: Is there any relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates’ lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities?

Table 5: Relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates’ lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	r _{value}	p _{value}
Human-Computer Interaction (HCI)		21.2840	3.10074			
Lecture attendance	213	58.2440	6.60816	211	.007	.001

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 5 revealed Mean, Standard Deviation and zero order correlation between the variables. It was observed that there was significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable in the order of ($r = 0.007$, $p < .05$). On this premise, the researcher concluded that there was positive relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates’ lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities.

Research Question 6: Is there any relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates’ punctuality in Ogun State Universities?

Table 6: Relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates’ punctuality in Ogun State Universities

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	r _{value}	p _{value}
Human-Computer Interaction (HCI)		21.2878	3.10			
Undergraduates’ punctuality	500	17.75	2.60	211	.022	.001

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 6 showed Mean, Standard Deviation and zero order correlation between the variables. It was observed that there was significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable in the order of ($r = 0.022$, $p < .05$). On this premise, the researcher concluded that there was positive relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates' punctuality in Ogun State Universities.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that there was high level of undergraduates' lecture attendance as well as punctuality for lectures in Ogun State Universities. These findings were in correlation with Ishola et al. (2022) who showed that there was presence of high level of undergraduates' lecture attendance and Fitzgerald (2021) showed some technology characteristics were associated with technostress, while some were not. The students' technostress could, however, not be determined to have an association with their perceived academic performance. Oladosu et al. (2020) revealed that as undergraduate students use smart devices, they become techno-stressed, and this is negatively influencing their learning with the devices. Adenekan (2024) revealed that the respondents experienced cognitive, affective and behavioural forms of techno stress, which had negative effect on their personal and professional development.

The findings of the study also indicated that allows students to have access to online materials, promotes students' behavior towards lecture attendance, shows case the benefits of lecture attendance to students, motivates undergraduates towards interactive computing among peer, always encourages to seeks further information on new issues and allows students to have access to online materials were among the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State universities. These findings concurred with the Wang et al. (2021) who showed that, in the past 20 years, the application of human-computer interaction not only made significant contributions to the development of hazard recognition, but also generated a series of new research subjects, such as multimodal physiological data analysis in hazard recognition experiments, development of intuitive devices and sensors, and the human-computer interaction safety management platform based on big data. Future research modules include computer vision, computer simulation, virtual reality, and ergonomics

Also, the findings revealed that guide undergraduates' interaction for lecture punctuality, teaches students on the need for computer for punctuality, helps students for self-evaluation that encourages lecture punctuality, improves the quality of interaction among students and computer that lead to lecture punctuality, and gives undergraduates' excellent experience between computer and its benefits for lecture punctuality were among the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture punctuality in Ogun State universities. These findings were in consonant with Ahmed et al. (2023) observed that all the institutions are aware of how importance HCI, and Computer information System (CIS) is and, how better it simplifies work. Also, basic modern ICT tools, devices and CIS for institutions of learning were highlighted and recommended to be deployed for improving learning efficiency and productivity.

There was significant relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities ($r = 0.007$, $p < .05$). These findings were in agreement with Fadare (2021) revealed that students' attendance and concentration in Mathematics classroom are directly and significantly related to their academic achievement in Mathematics ($p < 0.05$, $t_{cal} = 4.95 > 2.04 = t_{tab}$).

There was positive relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates' punctuality in Ogun State Universities ($r = 0.022$, $p < .05$). The findings were in consonant with Vera et al. (2022) revealed that the students displayed a positive attitude toward lecture attendance; male students resume lectures before female students but female students are more regular with lectures than their male counterparts; lecture attendance habits of students are attributed to completing assignments at the last minute, emergency travels, financial constraint, unconducive learning environment, availability of course outline on the textbook, student illness, students feel they can pass without attending classes and time fixed for class.

The findings also revealed that most students show a negative attitude toward lectures because they believe they can borrow lecture notes from fellow students, buy a textbook, create a study group or engage in personal reading; and that positive lecture attendance habit of students can be enhanced if the mark is awarded for attending lectures, making the learning environment more conducive and making students understand the need to attend lectures. The findings of the study further correlate with Auru and Gidado (2022) revealed that a significant relationship exists between lecture attendance and academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions. It also showed that a significant difference exists between the academic performance of business education students with high rate of attendance and those with low rate of attendance. The study concluded that lecture attendance enables students to be more creative, get first-hand and practical information from the teacher and it was found to be crucial to the acquisition of skills required for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance and punctuality in Ogun State Universities; the following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study that: there was high level of undergraduates' attendance for lectures in Ogun State Universities; there was high level of undergraduates' punctuality for lectures in Ogun State Universities; allows students to have access to online materials, promotes students' behavior towards lecture attendance, shows case the benefits of lecture attendance to students, motivates undergraduates towards interactive computing among peer, always encourages to seeks further information on new issues and allows students to have access to online materials were among the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State universities; also, the findings revealed that guide undergraduates' interaction for lecture punctuality, teaches students on the need for computer for punctuality, helps students for self-evaluation that encourages lecture punctuality, improves the quality of interaction among students and computer that lead to lecture punctuality, and gives undergraduates' excellent experience between computer and its benefits for lecture punctuality were among the impact of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) on undergraduates' lecture punctuality in Ogun State universities; there was significant relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates' lecture attendance in Ogun State Universities ($r = 0.007$, $p < .05$) and there was positive relationship between Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and undergraduates' punctuality in Ogun State Universities ($r = 0.022$, $p < .05$).

Recommendations

The following recommendations were raised in line with the findings of the study:

1. The study recommended that mandate the use of interactive technology, multimedia, and software in lectures to make classes inherently more engaging. This approach recognizes that

the current generation of students is more motivated to attend in-person sessions if technology is integrated effectively into the learning experience.

2. Adopt modern, automated attendance monitoring systems (e.g., those using facial recognition or QR codes) that are integrated with the main student database.
3. The system should be designed with a user-centric HCI approach, ensuring the check-in process is seamless, quick, and non-disruptive to the start of the lecture, thereby promoting punctuality.
4. Establish a policy framework for a "Student Affairs Committee" or similar body to monitor real-time attendance data from the HCI systems and trigger early interventions for students with lagging attendance.

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